

THE EFFECT OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE ON ORGANISATIONAL VALUE OF CONSUMER GOODS FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study assessed the effect of capital structure on the organizational value of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Specifically, it examined the effects of Short Term Debt (STD), Long Term Debt (LTD), and Total Equity (TEQ) on Profit for the Year (PFY) of these firms. Descriptive statistics, Unit Root tests, Pairwise Granger Causality tests, and Panel Least Squares Regression models were used to analyze ninety (90) panel data observations extracted from the audited annual reports of nine (9) firms selected from a population of twenty-one (21) consumer goods firms quoted on the Nigeria Exchange Group during the period 2013–2022. Research findings indicate that Short Term Debt (STD) positively and significantly affects Profit for the Year (PFY) {STD coefficient = 0.137544, p-value = 0.0003 (< 0.05)}. Findings also show that Total Equity (TEQ) positively and significantly affects Profit for the Year (PFY) {TEQ coefficient = 0.074695, p-value = 0.0273 (< 0.05)}. Results further reveal that Long Term Debt (LTD) positively but insignificantly affects Profit for the Year (PFY) {LTD coefficient = 0.018702, p-value = 0.5479 (> 0.05)}. The implication of these findings is that the firms are likely to witness growth in profitability as any of the explanatory variables increase. Based on these findings, the study recommends that consumer goods firms in Nigeria should meet their short-term business obligations and maximize firm value by using short-term debts, such as bank overdrafts, short-term loans, and trade credit, to finance their working capital needs. The study also recommends that firms increase returns on investment and organizational value by using long-term debt to finance long-term investments. However, debt financing should be limited to an optimal capital structure to avoid bankruptcy risk. Finally, the study recommends that firms improve profitability and organizational value by combining equity financing with debt financing to fund various business operations. Each firm should first identify its optimal capital structure in using debt and equity to finance its operations.*

Keywords: Short-term debts, long term debts, Total equity, Profit for the year, Consumer goods.

1. Introduction

In an attempt to maximize profit and create wealth for stakeholders, firm managers face many difficult decision areas in business. One such challenging decision is determining the appropriate proportion of debt and equity to use in financing business operations, commonly referred to as the capital structure decision. In this regard, firm managers remain conscious of the debt portion of the organization, which affects not only the organization's performance but also the market value of the firm (Black, 2015). Capital structure is described as the proportionate mix of debt and equity that an organization uses to meet its operational and investment needs. It represents the permanent and long-term financing framework and plays a major role in assessing an organization's financial health (Happay, 2024).

Khan et al. (2013) explained that the capital structure decision is a significant managerial choice, as it influences shareholders' returns and risks. The market price of shares is also affected by this decision, which companies must plan carefully from the time of promotion. Kumar et al. (2017) emphasized that choosing the optimal combination of debt and equity constitutes one of the most critical business decisions for a firm. This decision-making involves efficiently mixing different available financing sources, debt versus equity, to minimize the weighted average cost of capital. Abor (2005) stated that achieving an optimal capital structure involves balancing leverage's impact on the cost of capital and overall firm value. This mix of debt and equity aims to minimize the weighted average cost of capital, reflecting a proportional blend of long-term funding sources, including loans, preferred equity, common stock, and retained earnings.

Loth and Heller (2022) identified several measures of capital structure, including equity capital, long-term loans, short-term loans, debt-to-equity ratio, debt-to-assets ratio, long-term debt-to-capitalization ratio, and interest coverage ratio, among others. Equity refers to a company's common and preferred stock plus retained earnings. Mishkin (2013) defined equity capital as a business's net worth, raised either through the sale of new stock or retained earnings. Kinlo and Egbetunde (2010) described long-term debt as debts and financial obligations lasting more than one year. For a company, this includes any financing or leasing obligations due after a 12-month period. Ganti (2020) described short-term debt, also known as current liabilities, as debts that a company plans to pay off within one year.

A scan of the available literature suggests that considerable research has already been conducted in this area. However, most recent studies appear to focus primarily on the effect of capital structure on the financial performance and profitability of firms. Little or no attention has been paid to the effect of capital structure on firm value. While financial performance and profitability are crucial in the study of firms, firm value is equally important because it represents the net worth of a business and determines

its long-term survival. In view of this, studying the effect of capital structure on firm value is essential to address this perceived research gap.

Statement of the Problem

In the study of capital structure, Myers (1977) noted in the trade-off theory that every company has an optimal capital structure that must be determined by balancing the benefits and drawbacks of debt and equity. A firm chooses how much debt capital and how much equity capital to include in its capital structure by evaluating the advantages and disadvantages of each source.

According to the theory, the optimal capital structure is the perfect mix of debt and equity financing that maximizes the company's market value while minimizing its cost of capital.

Despite the importance of capital structure theories in increasing firm value, most firms in Nigeria—particularly manufacturing firms—find it difficult to implement an optimal capital structure in practice. This is because, even after companies identify their optimal capital structure, they often lack access to debt financing due to stringent conditions imposed by financial institutions in the country for extending credit facilities. As a result, some firms resort to equity financing only, even when debt financing is necessary to attain the optimal capital structure. The consequence is an inappropriate mix of debt and equity, leading to poor returns on investment. Some consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria have even exited the market due to a lack of access to loanable funds.

The present study was motivated by this ongoing situation to examine the effect of capital structure on the organizational value of Nigerian consumer goods firms.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to determine the effect of capital structure on organizational value of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of short-term debts on profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.
- ii. Analyze the effect of long-term debt on profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.
- iii. Appraise the effect of total equity on profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

Research Questions

The specific objectives were guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the effect of short-term debts on profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms?
- ii. To what extent does long-term debt affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms?
- iii. How does total equity affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to address the research questions:

- i. Short term debts do not significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.
- ii. Long term debts do not significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

iii. Total equity does not significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

Significance of the Study

Firm Managers: The study will be of importance to consumer goods firm managers in Nigeria in their financing decisions. In particular, the study will assist the managers navigate through the harsh economic environment of the country.

Investors: Firms that obtain the appropriate mixture of debt and equity will maximize profitability and increase firms value. Such firms are the attraction of investors. Therefore, the study will assist the investors make investment decision.

Researchers: This study will also be of importance to researchers, especially academic researchers because the researchers will find important citation from the study which will be referenced while conducting more studies in related areas.

Scope of the Study

The primary focus of the study is on the effect of capital structure on organizational value of Nigeria consumer goods firms during the period from 2013 to 2022. Short term debts, long-term debt and total equity are the independent variables of the study and measures of capital structure while profit for the year is the dependent variable and surrogate for organizational value.

2. Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Capital Structure

Sharma and Vaidya (2024) described capital structure as the combination of debts and equity, which a company uses to finance its investment and operations. It represents how a company raises its funds to support its activities and growth. A company's capital structure includes various forms of debts, such as loans and bonds as well as equity, such as common and preferred stock. The best capital structure is an optimal capital structure. Horsefall (2021) described optimal capital structure as the combination of various debts and equity in a countless mixture to come across a particular combination that maximizes a firm's overall value. Optimal capital structure is the perfect mix of debt and equity financing that helps in maximizing the value of a company in the market while at the same time minimizes its cost of capital. It is a minimum weighted average cost of capital at which the value of a firm is maximized. The goal of determining an optimal capital structure is to strike a balance between risk and return, minimizing the cost of capital while maximizing shareholders value.

Younus, et al (2014) opined that researchers in finance are still unable to find a model that can help in determining an optimal capital structure despite the fact that there are many theories explaining it. Usually, capital structure policy depends upon the company's size, ownership, profitability, various costs, earning growth and liquidity of company's assets. Barges (2009) stated that effective utilization

of limited capital resources is crucial for optimal business operations and maximum returns. Capital structure requires careful consideration of its composition. Various financial instruments, such as debt, equity, and preference shares, serve as funding sources, each entailing specific rights and risks for investors and debtors. Orwel (2010) noted that the two main sources of financing which are available to a firm are either internal or external sources of funds. The internal sources, the equity capital include ordinary and preference shares, reserves, and retained earnings. The external sources include both short and long-term debts in the form of debt financing.

Short Term Debts

Ganti (2020) described short-term debt also known as current liabilities, as the debts that a company has that it plans to pay off within one year. Short term debts are listed in the statement of financial position under the current liabilities part of the total liabilities. Khartit (2020) identified accounts payable, trade payables, bank overdraft and all overdue payments owed to stakeholders and outside vendors as some of the examples of short-term debts. A commercial paper issued by a company to finance inventories, receivables, and short-term obligations like payroll is also an example of short-term debt. Makanga (2015) stated that short-term debts boost a business to have ample cash to enhance smooth and efficient operation. However, short-term debts and financial performance are intertwined and, therefore, higher short-term debts cause operational ineffectiveness.

Guin (2011) explained that short-term debts are used to finance current assets that can be quickly turned back into cash; examples of this type of debt are accounts receivable and inventories. Non-current liabilities in the form of long-term debt, or debts, are used to finance long-term assets, such as the purchase of land and the construction of a building. Short-term assets should be financed with short-term debts while long-term assets should be financed with long-term debts.

Tunj et al (2015) opined that for a firm to remain in business for long, it has to use mixed capital. Nevertheless, debt capital has to be used reasonably as highly levered companies have large amount of interest to pay annually.

Long Term Debts

Edore and Ujuju (2020) described long term debt as an amount owed exceeding 12 months' period. A company lists its long-term debt on its statement of financial position under liabilities usually under a sub heading for long term liabilities. Long term debt could be in the form of a bank loan, mortgage bonds, debenture, long term leases, trade and business financing, Loan Company's bond issue or other obligations not due for one year. Such debt consists mostly of bonds or similar obligations, including a great variety of notes, capital lease obligation and mortgage issue. Kpodar and Gbenyo (2010) opined that long-term debts are suitable for high-return projects that require a continuing commitment of capital for years. Those investments take more time to complete but contribute more to productivity growth than short-term investments. For example, short-term loans may be used to maintain

equipment, while long-term loans may be used to build a new plant, invest in research and development, or adopt a new technology.

Shubita and Alsawalhah (2012) noted that good example of long-term debt is bond. A firm may issue bonds to raise funds for a variety of reasons, such as to raise capital for new capital projects. Bond sales bring in immediate income, but the company ends up paying for the use of investors' capital due to interest payments. Vätavu (2015) stated that debt is cheaper than equity, such that a firm can increase its firm value by employing debt financing up to a reasonable limit. Debt is preferred over equity for two circumstantial reasons: the cost of debt financing is far lower than that of equity and the tax-shield benefit of debts.

Total Equity

Horsefall (2021) defined equity capital as the ownership capital of the company. It is the permanent capital and cannot be withdrawn during the lifetime of the business. With equity financing through ordinary shares, you can reduce or increase your ownership percentage in a firm through the sale or purchase of ordinary shares to/from one or more individuals or entities in exchange for a specified amount of money. Mishkin (2013) stated that a business equity capital is important because it protects the business against a decline in the value of its assets, which could force it into bankruptcy. Rose and Hudgins (2008) explained that a high equity capital ratio fosters public trust and reassures stakeholders that the firm will always be financially sound enough to meet its business obligations regardless of the state of the economy.

Velnampy and Niresh (2012) stated that the proportion of debt and equity is a strategic choice of corporate managers and it is a significant managerial decision because it influences the shareholder's return and risk. Consequently, the market value of a share may be affected by the capital structure decision, and the company will have to plan its capital structure initially, at the time of its inception. Nawaz et al (2011) identified two components of equity capital, which consists of contributed capital, which is the money that was originally invested in the business in exchange for shares of stock or ownership and retained earnings, which represent profits from past years that have been kept by the company and used to strengthen the statement of financial position or fund growth, acquisitions and expansion.

Organizational Value

Luh and Luh (2019) described firm value as certain conditions that had been achieved by the firm in return for public trust toward the firm after going through a process of several years since it was founded. Khasawneh and Staytieh (2017) stated the price a buyer can pay if the firm is sold is the definition of company value. Share prices can reflect the value of a firm. A high stock price indicates that the firm's value is higher. The tool that can be used to measure firm value is Price Book Value, which is a comparison between the market value of stocks and the book value of stocks. Hasnawati (2005)

noted that the company's value is affected by factors of financing decision, dividend policy, external factors such as inflation rates, foreign exchange rates, economic growth, political and market psychology.

Ikpesu and Eboiyehi (2018) argued that capital structure is one of the factors affecting firm value. Capital structure is the proportion of debt in a company's capital. It indicates the amount of debts in relation to equity used in funding a firm. Sudiani and Wiksuana (2018) also agreed that the first factor affecting firm value is profitability. Profitability is a measure of the effectiveness of a company and is used to measure the company's ability to obtain profits. Mahendra (2011) also confirmed that profitability significantly influences firm value since the higher the profitability the higher the profit sharing is guaranteed. Sudiyatno, et al (2020) affirmed that firms' performance is the basis of information for investors in making investment decisions. Firms with good performance will get a positive response from investors, by being willing to pay a higher price for the companies' shares. With high share price, the firm value or shareholder wealth also increases.

Profit for the Year

Ventureline (2017) described profit for the year as the net profit earned by the company after deducting all expenses like interest, depreciation and tax. Profit for the year could be fully retained by a company to be used in the business or used for dividends, if declared, and paid to the shareholders from this residue. Hermi (2004) opined that profit was obtained from difference between the incoming treasures (revenue and profit) and outlay (expenses and losses). Aldridge (2015) explained that profit for the year could be fully retained by a company to be used in the business or distributed as dividends, if declared to the shareholders. Putra and Lestari (2016) opined that profit for the year figure was considered the best measure of the ability of an entity to generate a return, since it incorporated both operating income and income from other sources, such as interest income.

Fig 2.1: Conceptual Framework Summary

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025

Theoretical Framework

The study was conducted from the point of view of two theories, namely: Trade-Off Theory developed by Myers in 1977 and Agency Theory propounded by Jensen and Meckling in 1976. The study is, however, anchored on Trade-Off Theory, because of its appropriate connection with the primary objective of the study.

The Trade-Off Theory

The Trade-Off Theory was developed by Myers in 1977. The theory states that every company has an optimal capital structure that may be determined by balancing the benefits and drawbacks of equity. A firm chooses how much debt capital and how much equity capital to include in its capital structure by evaluating the benefits and drawbacks of each source. While having a lot of debt in the capital structure might result in agency fees and insolvency, debt capital also offers tax deductions. Information asymmetry and the competing interests of many company stakeholders result in agency costs. Meckling and Jensen (1976) stated that through the integration of agency costs into the trade-off theory a company can ascertain its optimal financial configuration by balancing the benefits of debt (like tax advantages) against the drawbacks of excessive debt (like financial distress) and the ensuing agency costs for equity versus debt. The theory states that a company's capital structure shouldn't be more debt-heavy than it needs to be because doing so will raise the cost of debt relative to its benefit.

Agency Theory

Meckling and Jensen (1976) proposed the agency theory, which is characterized by a specific percentage of debt in the organization's financial structure that lowers agency costs resulting from disagreements between managers and firm owners (Leland, 1998). Agency expenses would decrease as a result of fewer disagreements between agencies, which would lead to an increase in revenue. A company's use of debt can help control and supervise managers to ensure that they pursue objectives that are beneficial to the business. Buferna, et al (2005) noted that the inclusion of debt in the financial structure motivates firm managers to support a company's expansion in order to provide cash flows that would finance debt payments. Dawar (2014) observed that the company becomes more profitable as a result. This theory holds that employing debt, whether it be short-term or otherwise, reduces agency conflicts between managers and shareholders of a company, which promotes economic progress of the firm.

Empirical Review

Short Term Debts and Organizational Value

Pyoko and Muchiri (2024) studied free cash flow and short-term debt of firms listed at the Nairobi securities exchange Kenya during 2007-2011 periods. The sample consist of 27 firms that had been listed for less than five years at the Nairobi Stock Exchange. The study applied secondary data obtained from the firms from 2007-2011. The data were initially analyzed using pooled ordinary least squares regression model and also panel data regression analysis. The result showed a positive and significant

relationship between free cash flow and short-term debt of firms. In line with the result, it was recommended that managers of listed firms on NSE should assess the company's overall financial flexibility and short-term debt needs to determine the optimal balance between free cash flow and short-term debt as excessive reliance on free cash flow for short term debt repayment may increase vulnerability

Kiprotich (2022) studied the effect of short-term debt financing on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Bomet County, Kenya during 2017-2021. The study targeted a population of 75 SMEs in the county. The independent variables and measures of short-term debt are, overdraft, short term loans, trade credit and lease financing. A sample of 59 of the SMEs were drawn using simple random sampling. Hence, secondary data relating to SMEs overdraft, lease finance, trade credit and performance was collected over a period 5years (from 2017 to 2021). Descriptive statistics, correlation, regression analysis and analysis of variance were used to examine the data collected. Results of analysis suggest that overdraft positively and significantly affect financial performance of the SMEs, Short term loans negatively and significantly affect financial performance of the SMEs. Trade credit positively and significantly affect financial performance of the SMEs. Lease financing positively, but non-significantly affect financial performance of the SMEs.

Oranefo and Egbunike (2022) examined the effect of debt financing on the firm valuation of quoted non-financial firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange during 2011-2019. Specifically, the study analyzed the effect of short-term debt to equity, long-term debt to equity, and total debt to assets on Tobin's Q. The sample consists of seventy-five (75) non-financial firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange during the period. The secondary data obtained from MachameRATIOS were analyzed using panel regression techniques. Unlike prior studies, the study also employs the Arellano Bond Dynamic Panel-data Estimation Model for robustness analysis. Research results show that there is a negative effect of short-term debt to equity on Tobin's Q. The effect of long-term debt to equity and total debt to assets was positive and significant.

Hajisaaid (2020) studied the effect of capital structure on profitability of basic materials sector of Saudi Arabia firms during the period from 2009 to 2018. The dependent variable is the return on equity (ROE). In contrast, independent variables are a short-term debt to total assets ratio (SDA), long-term debt to total assets ratio (LDA), and total debt to total assets ratio (DA). The sample consists of all basic materials shareholding companies with share price data available during the study period. The data collected from the selected firms were analyzed using Descriptive statistics and panel data regression analysis, fixed effect model, random effect model, and Hausman test. The results indicate a negative relationship between short-term debt to total assets ratio (SDA) and profitability. Results also show a significantly positive relationship between short-term debt and profitability 0.878. A significantly

positive association is between long-term debt and profitability 0.638. A significantly positive association is between total debt and profitability 0.616.

Shikumo, et al (2020) evaluated the effect of short-term debt on financial growth of non-financial firms listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange. The target population of the study comprised of 45 non-financial firms listed at the NSE for a period of ten years from 2008 to 2017. Financial firms were excluded because of their specific sector characteristics and stringent regulatory framework. Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis were used to examine the secondary data collected from the audited annual financial statement of the selected firms. The result indicates that, short term debt explains 45.99% and 25.6% of variations in financial growth as measured by growth in earnings per share and growth in market capitalization respectively. Short term debt positively and significantly influences financial growth measured using both growth in earnings per share and growth in market capitalization. The study recommends that, the management of non-financial firms should employ financing means that can improve the earnings per share, market capitalization and enhance the value of the firm for the benefit of its stakeholders.

Long Term Debts and Organizational Value

Ariyo-Edu (2023) examined the impact of capital structure on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study employs both descriptive and inferential statistics and data were analyzed using a multiple regression model. The finding shows a noticeably inverse relationship between overall debt and profitability. It was also found that a higher debt position will result in lower profitability; the more debt, the less profitable the company will be. Results show that debt and profitability are negatively correlated. Because of the high-interest rates, profitability tends to decrease in cases of increased debt. The study suggests that to boost the profitability of manufacturing enterprises, a suitable mix of capital structures should be adjusted.

Atieno (2023) the effect of long-term debt financing on the profitability of commercial airlines in Kenya. The census sampling technique was adopted for the study, thus every commercial airline was used to establish the effect of long-term debt management on profitability. Secondary data were collected from audited financial statements of the airlines and analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlational and panel data regression analysis. Research results indicates that long-term debt financing has a negative and statistically significant effect on the profitability of commercial airlines in Kenya. This is supported by a regression coefficient of -0.2318 and a p-value of 0.038. The study recommends that executives of commercial airlines should aim to have a long-term debt that is manageable by the company and ensure that the long-term debt load is compatible with a favorable long-term debt ratio for the company to function without worrying about defaulting on loans.

Amankwah et al. (2021) conducted a study to investigate the impact of debt financing on performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ghana from 2015-2019. The study targeted a population of forty-

two (42) SMEs in Ghana Stock Exchange during the period. Out of this population, eight (8) SMEs were selected based on their stated capital of not less than GHC 300,000. A five-year time frame financial account reports from 2015 -2019 consecutive year period were used for this study. Multiple regression analysis was used to examine the time series data extracted from the annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms. Research results suggest that debt-financed through both short and long term have a detrimental impact on SMEs' financial performance. The study recommends that SMEs utilize their debt significantly.

Horsefall (2021) investigated the relationship between equity financing practices and profitability of consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study proxied equity financing and profitability using Return on Assets, Return on Capital Employed and gross profit margin. The study targeted a population of twenty (20) consumer goods manufacturing firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group during the period. Out of this population a sample of nineteen (19) consumer goods manufacturing firms were sampled for the study. The time series data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms were analyzed using single regression analysis. Findings from the analysis suggest that a significant relationship between equity financing and variables of profitability (ROA, ROCE and GPM). The study also found out that there is a significant relationship between debt financing and variables of profitability (ROA, ROCE and GPM). On the other hand, equity/debt financing significantly relates to ROA and GPM but does not significantly relate to ROCE. The study recommends that management of Nigeria listed consumer goods firms should work hard to optimize the capital structure of their firms in order to increase the profitability of the firm and enhance firm's value.

Hasan; et al (2020) carried out a study to analyze the effect of debt financing on firm profitability of manufacturing companies in Malaysia during 2010-2018 periods. The independent variables were debt ratio, long term debt and short-term debt while the dependent variable was the return on equity and used to measure the firm's performance. The sample consists of 23 companies listed in Malaysia Stock Exchange during eight (8) years period (2010 -2018). The secondary data obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and panel data regression analysis. Findings show that there is significant relationship on debt financing towards firm profitability. The findings will be useful for policymaker and listed manufacturing companies in Malaysia to make better debt financing decisions.

Edore and Ujuju (2020) investigated the effect of financial leverage on the value of firms in Nigeria during the period from 2000 to 2017. The independent variables of the study are long-term debts, medium term debts and short term debts while the dependent variable is the value of the firm. The sample comprised of five (5) public companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange during the period. Secondary data were obtained from the annual reports and financials statements of the selected

companies and analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient and Ordinary Least Squares regression analysis. Results of analysis suggest that long term debt has a significant positive effect on the value of the companies' performance. Medium term debt and short term debts have significant positive influence on value of the companies and were statistically significant. The researcher also found out that the use of leverage enhances the value of the firm. Therefore, it was recommended that firms should go ahead and finance their operations with long term debt, medium term debts and short term debts when the need arises in order to ensure that value is enhanced.

Total Equity and Organizational Value

Yu and Kim (2023) analyzed the effects of profitability and debt-to-equity ratio on operating leverage in the case of companies listed on the Korea Exchange from 2000 to 2021. The number of firm-year observations for the firms that fulfilled the sampling conditions was 29,486. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, regression and correlation analysis. Results of analysis suggest that there was a positive correlation between profitability and debt-to-equity ratio for Korean firms, which means that their capital structure can be explained by the pecking order theory. That is, the more profitable a company is, the more it prefers to raise funds through debt issuance rather than equity issuance. In the case of Korean companies with a relatively high dependence on debt, the increase in operating leverage for facility investment among other business activities mostly expands debt, and the higher the profitability, the higher the debt-to-equity ratio is.

Onyema (2021) appraised the impact of debt financing on profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The independent variables of the study and measure of debt financing are long term debts, total debts, Tobin Q Ratio Profitability, firm size is the independent variable while assets growth and assets tangibility are the control variable. Panel regression was employed to examine the data obtained from the selected firms. Findings indicate that the quoted firms are listed on the Nigeria stock exchange. Findings further reveals that debt financing is statistically significant in determining profitability of manufacturing firms in the quoted firms in Nigeria. The regression results indicate that long term debt, total debt, Tobin Q and profitability are important in influencing the profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. A well-managed capital structure in terms of debt financing, leads to an increase in the profitability of the firms as showed in the result.

Xuan, et al (2021) studied the impact of equity capital on the bank's profitability in the Vietnam's Banking System during the period from 2008 to 2019. The sample consists of 24 Vietnamese commercial banks listed on the Stock Exchange during the period. The data obtained from the selected firms were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression analysis. Research findings indicate that, when ROAA and ROAE are used to measure the bank's profit, the equity capital ratio (CAP) has a statistically significant positive effect on the ROAA while having a negative effect on the ROAE. Between 2013 and 2019, the CAP variable has a positive effect on the ROAA and ROAE,

indicating that banks with a larger equity capital ratio achieved higher profitability. Furthermore, the deposits-to-assets ratio (DTA) and loan-loss reserves ratio (LLR) both have a negative effect on both proxies for bank profitability, although bank size (SIZE) has a negligible effect on bank profits in the majority of circumstances. Additionally, the rate of GDP growth and inflation (INF) have a beneficial effect on the bank's profitability. The study's objective is to present some critical policy implications for bank executives about the importance of adequate equity capital for the bank's sustainability development.

Zemenu (2021) investigated the empirical relationship between capital structure, as measured by total and short-term debt ratios, and profitability of private banks in Ethiopia, during the period 2013/14 to 2018/19. A survey of 16 private banks is included in the study. Based on the regression fixed effect analysis results, capital structure variables and some bank-specific characteristics explain a substantial part of the variations in bank profitability. Higher profitability measures of ROA and net interest margin tend to be associated with relatively higher total and short-term debt ratios, loan to deposit ratios, and credit risks. Besides, older banks are in a better position than younger counterparts in terms of profitability. The impact of size is found to be significantly negative, at least for the ROA model, implying that Ethiopian private banks are operating below their optimal capacity. Mixed results were found pertaining to coefficient estimates of cos-income ratio and employee productivity.

Rahman; et al (2020) empirically examined the impact of financial leverage on firm's profitability in the listed textile sector of Bangladesh. Firm profitability is measured by return on equity and both short term debt and long term debt are used as the proxies of financial leverage. The sample consists of 22 DSE listed textile firms has been used to conduct the study. Pooled Ordinary Least Squares, Fixed Effect and Generalized Method of Moments models were used to test the relationship between financial leverage and profitability of firms. Results show a significant negative relationship between leverage and firm's profitability using the Pooled OLS method. The result is also consistent with the fixed effect and GMM method. This suggest implies that firm's profitability is negatively affected by the firm's capital structure.

Gaps in Empirical Review

The findings from the empirical review indicate that out of the sixteen (16) recent studies examined in this area, only five (5) were conducted in Nigeria, while the remaining eleven (11) were carried out in other countries. The review also shows that none of the sixteen (16) studies focused specifically on consumer goods firms within any of the respective economies. Furthermore, none of the studies covered the period from 2021 to 2022. It was also found that only two (2) of the sixteen (16) studies examined the effect of capital structure on firm value, as most of the research focused on the relationship between capital structure and firm profitability. These identified gaps in the empirical literature motivated the

present study to examine the effect of capital structure on the organizational value of Nigerian consumer goods firms during the period 2013–2022.

3. Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted *ex-post facto* researcher design. Therefore, existing financial data were extracted from the audited annual financial statements of the selected listed consumer good’s firms in Nigeria and were used to conduct the study.

Area of Study

This study was specifically conducted on consumer goods firms listed on Nigeria Exchange Group during the period from 2013 to 2022.

Sources of Data

The source of data for the study is secondary data, which were collected from the audited annual financial statements of the selected consumer goods firms listed on Nigeria Exchange Group during the period from 2013 to 2022.

Population

A total of twenty-one (21) consumer goods firms were listed on Nigeria Exchange Group during the period. The twenty-one firms constituted the population of the study.

Sample Size Determination

The sampling method adopted for the study is purposive sampling. This sampling method was informed by data availability as some of the consumer goods firms did not use debt financing during the period. Some used only long term debt financing while some used only short term financing. The purposive sampling technique was therefore used to select nine (9) consumer goods firms that used both long and short term financing during the period. The firms that satisfied this criterion and were selected are: Guinness Nigeria Plc, Nigeria Breweries Plc, International Breweries Plc, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Unilever Nigeria Plc, Dangote Sugar Plc, UAC Nigeria Plc, Vitafoam Plc and Nigeria Flourmill Plc.

Model Specification

The following model was developed in accordance with the independent and dependent variable of the study:

$$PFY = \beta_0 + \beta_1(STD) + \beta_2(LTD) + \beta_3(TEQ) + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots i$$

Where:

PFY = Profit for the Year

STD = Short Term Debts

LTD = Long Term Debt

TEQ = Total Equity

β = Beta

ε = error term

Method of Data Analysis

The statistical tool adopted for the study are: Descriptive Statistics, Unit Root Test, Pairwise Granger Causality Test and Panel Least Square Regression Analysis. Least Square Regression Analysis is the main tool of analysis, which was used to testing the three null hypotheses formulated for the study. R^2 was used to test the extent by which the independent variables explained the dependent variable (Profit for the Year). Long Term Debt, Short Debt Term Debts and Total Equity were the independent variables and measures of capital structure while Profit for The Year is the dependent variable and measure of organizational value.

4. Results

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics, Unit Root test, Pairwise Granger Causality test and Panel Least Square Regression Model were employed to analyze the secondary data extracted from the selected consumer goods firms. The results of these analysis are presented in the tables below.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	PFY	STD	LTD	TEQ
Mean	11014063	26139652	21319610	73016847
Median	7409227.	10906087	4177853.	65956849
Maximum	54742134	1.91E+08	1.54E+08	1.96E+08
Minimum	-27790665	0.000000	0.000000	2706458.
Std. Dev.	15755557	40347362	38874449	55163802
Skewness	0.705167	2.444704	2.351882	0.597789
Kurtosis	3.391741	8.668133	7.562447	2.268721
Jarque-Bera Probability	8.034384 0.018003	210.1276 0.000000	161.0299 0.000000	7.365657 0.025152
Sum	9.91E+08	2.35E+09	1.92E+09	6.57E+09
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.21E+16	1.45E+17	1.34E+17	2.71E+17
Observations	90	90	90	90

Source: Eviews 11.0 Output, 2025.

Descriptive Statistics in table 1 reveals that the mean of the variables are: 11014063, 26139652, 21319610 and 73016847 for Profit for the Year (PFY), Short Term Debts (STD), Long Term Debts (LTD) and total Equity. Similarly, the Standard Deviations of the variables as observed from the table are: 15755557, 40347362, 38874449 and 55163802 for PFY, STD, LTD and LEQ respectively. Looking at these results, one could observe that most of the Standard Deviations are above the Mean scores of the variables. This is a sign of high volatility in the variables during the period covered by the study. The

Maximum and Minimum values of the variables exhibited positive positions during the period except PFY with a minimum value of -27790665. This negative PFY means that some of the nine firms made losses during the period. However, no firm witnessed any negative total equity during the period. The distribution of the data set was tested using Jacque Bera Statistics, Skewness and Kurtosis tests. The results show that the data set used for the study are normally distributed, especially from the Jarque-Bera Statistics with the p-value of all the variables less than 0.05 (p-value<0.05).

Table 2: Levin, Lin & Chu t*

Null Hypothesis: Unit root (common unit root process)
 Series: PFY
 Date: 06/20/24 Time: 17:32
 Sample: 2013 2022
 Exogenous variables: Individual effects
 User-specified lags: 1
 Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel
 Total (balanced) observations: 72
 Cross-sections included: 9

Method	Statistic	Prob.**
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-2.11226	0.0173

** Probabilities are computed assuming asymptotic normality

Intermediate results on PFY

Cross section	2nd Stage Coefficient	Variance of Reg	HAC of Dep.	Lag	Max Lag	Bandwidth	Obs
1	-1.57154	4.E+13	4.E+13	1	1	8.0	8
2	-0.23699	3.E+13	4.E+13	1	1	0.0	8
3	-0.53877	9.E+13	9.E+13	1	1	1.0	8
4	-0.38272	1.E+14	2.E+13	1	1	8.0	8
5	-1.25293	2.E+13	7.E+12	1	1	8.0	8
6	-0.55523	2.E+14	4.E+13	1	1	8.0	8
7	-0.74412	2.E+13	7.E+12	1	1	8.0	8
8	-0.23935	4.E+11	9.E+11	1	1	1.0	8
9	-0.66681	4.E+13	2.E+13	1	1	4.0	8

	Coefficient	t-Stat	SE Reg	mu*	sig*	Obs
Pooled	-0.44070	-4.548	1.110	-0.554	0.919	72

Source: Eviews 11.0 Output, 2025

The usefulness of Unit Root test is its importance in detecting the presence of unit root in a time series data. The presence of a unit root in a regression model leads to spurious regression. In view of this, Unit Root test is used as a diagnostic statistical tool in a regression model to search for the presence of a unit

root in the model. Results of the Levin, Lin & Chu t*Unit Root test in table 2 show that all the variables of the study are integrated of order $O(0)$ with p-value = 0.0173. This finding suggest that all the variables have zero-unit root during the period, as all integrated in the same order, signifying a co-integration among the four variables of the study.

Table 3: Pairwise Granger Causality Test

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 06/20/24 Time: 17:34

Sample: 2013 2022

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
STD does not Granger Cause PFY	72	0.20451	0.8156
PFY does not Granger Cause STD		0.68370	0.5082
LTD does not Granger Cause PFY	72	0.15308	0.8584
PFY does not Granger Cause LTD		0.95124	0.3914
TEQ does not Granger Cause PFY	72	0.91082	0.4071
PFY does not Granger Cause TEQ		1.49578	0.2315
LTD does not Granger Cause STD	72	8.60086	0.0005
STD does not Granger Cause LTD		7.26455	0.0014
TEQ does not Granger Cause STD	72	5.91471	0.0043
STD does not Granger Cause TEQ		2.49683	0.0900
TEQ does not Granger Cause LTD	72	2.70179	0.0744
LTD does not Granger Cause TEQ		17.1268	1.E-06

Source: Eviews 11.0 Output, 2025

The Granger Causality test is a statistical hypothesis test for determining whether one time series is useful in forecasting another. A time series X is said to Granger-cause Y , if it can be shown that those X values provide statistically significant information about future values of Y . Based on this, we interpreted the results of the Granger Causality tests in table 3.

- i. The table indicates that the granger p-value of STD on PFY is 0.8156 while the granger p-value of PFY on STD is 0.5082. These results suggest that STD does not granger cause PFY, just the same way as PFY does not granger cause STD.
- ii. The table equally reveals that the granger p-value of LTD on PFY is 0.8584 while the granger p-value of PFY on LTD is 0.3914. These results means that LTD does not granger cause PFY, just the same way as PFY does not granger cause LTD.

iii. The table further disclosed that the granger p-value of LEQ on PFY is 0.4071 while the granger p-value of PFY on LEQ is 0.2315. These results imply that LEQ does not granger cause PFY, the same way as PFY does not granger cause LEQ.

Table 4: Pane Least Square Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: PFY
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 06/20/24 Time: 17:30
Sample: 2013 2022
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 9
Total panel (balanced) observations: 90

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
STD	0.137544	0.035972	3.823655	0.0003
LTD	0.018702	0.030986	0.603576	0.5479
TEQ	0.074695	0.033212	2.249034	0.0273
C	9554168.	2624046.	3.641006	0.0005
R-squared	0.705477	Mean dependent var		11014063
Adjusted R-squared	0.663941	S.D. dependent var		15755557
S.E. of regression	9133588.	Akaike info criterion		35.01638
Sum squared resid	6.51E+15	Schwarz criterion		35.34969
Log likelihood	-1563.737	Hannan-Quinn criter.		35.15079
F-statistic	16.98496	Durbin-Watson stat		1.924765
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: *Eview11.0* **Output,** **2025.**

Table 4 contains the Panel Least Square Regression results of the nine (9) selected consumer goods firms in Nigeria during the period. The table indicates that Adjusted Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of the model is 0.705477. This result means that about 71% of the changes in the Profit for the Year of the firms can be explained by the explanatory variables, comprising, Short Term Debts (STD), Long Term Debts (LTD) and Total Equity (TEQ) while the remaining 29% can be explained by other variable, quantitative and qualitative, included in the model of the study. Durbin Watson Statistics results in the table also reveal that there is no autocorrelation in the model of the study, as observed from the Durbin Watson Coefficient is 1.924765, which is approximated to the lower limit of 2 in the benchmark range of 2-4.

Test of Hypotheses

Decision Rule: P-value (α) = 0.05. Reject the null hypothesis if the p-value of the regression coefficient is less than 0.05, otherwise accept the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis One

Restating of the Hypothesis in Null and Alternate Forms

H₀: Short term debts do not significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

H₁: Short term debts significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

Decision: The regression model in table 4 shows that the p-value of Short Term Debts (STD) is 0.0003, and this value is less than 0.05 significance level ($0.0003 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted, which states that Short Term Debt significantly affect Profit for The Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Restating of the Hypothesis in Null and Alternate Forms

H₀: Long term debts do not significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

H₁: Long term debts significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

Decision: The regression model further indicate that the p-value of Long Term Debts (LTD) is 0.5479, and this value is greater than 0.05 significance level ($0.5479 > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, which states that Long Term Debt does not significantly affect Profit for The Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Restating of the Hypothesis in Null and Alternate Forms

H₀: Total equity does not significantly effect on profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

H₁: Total equity significantly affect profit for the year of Nigeria consumer goods firms.

Decision: The regression model also disclosed that the p-value of Total Equity (TEQ) is 0.0273, and this value is less than 0.05 significance level ($0.0003 < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted, which states that Total Equity significantly affect Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Short Term Debts and Organizational Value

The findings from the Regression Model in table 4 show that the regression coefficient of Short Term Debts (STD) is positive at 0.137544 while the p-value is 0.0003 ($0.0003 < 0.05$). Based on these findings, the study asserts that Short Term Debts positively and significantly affects Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This result is not consistent with the granger causality test STD does not granger cause PFY. However, the result is consistent with The Trade-Off Theory developed by Myers in 1977. The theory states that every company has an optimal capital structure that may be determined by balancing the benefits and drawbacks of equity. The theory argued that a company can ascertain its optimal financial configuration by balancing the benefits of debt (like tax advantages)

against the drawbacks of excessive debt (like financial distress) and the ensuing agency costs for equity versus debt.

The result is also consistent with: Kiprotich (2022) who found that Short term loans negatively and significantly affect financial performance of the SMEs. Hajisaaid (2020) who found that there is a significantly positive relationship between short-term debt and profitability 0.878. A significantly positive association is between long-term debt and profitability 0.638. Shikumo, et al (2020) who noted that short term debt positively and significantly influences financial growth measured using both growth in earnings per share and growth in market capitalization. Hasan; et al (2020) who noted that there is significant relationship on debt financing towards firm profitability.

Edore and Ujuju (2020) who found that long term debt has a significant positive effect on the value of the companies' performance. Medium term debt and short term debts have significant positive influence on value of the companies and were statistically significant. Onyema (2021) who found that debt financing is statistically significant in determining profitability of manufacturing firms in the quoted firms in Nigeria. This result differs from: Oranefo and Egbunike (2022) who observed a negative effect of short-term debt to equity on Tobin's Q. The effect of long-term debt to equity and total debt to assets was positive and significant. Ariyo-Edu (2023) who concluded that debt and profitability are negatively correlated. Amankwah; et al (2021) who found that debt-financed through both short and long term have a detrimental impact on SMEs' financial performance.

Long Term Debts and Organizational Value

The findings from the Regression Model also confirmed that the regression coefficient of Long Term Debts (LTD) is positive at 0.018702 while the p-value is 0.5479 ($0.5479 > 0.05$). Based on these findings, the study concludes that Long Term Debts positively, but insignificantly affects Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This result differs from the granger causality test, because the LTD does not granger cause PFY. The result, is however, consistent with The Trade-Off Theory developed by Myers in 1977. The theory states that every company has an optimal capital structure that may be determined by balancing the benefits and drawbacks of equity. The theory argued that a company can ascertain its optimal financial configuration by balancing the benefits of debt (like tax advantages) against the drawbacks of excessive debt (like financial distress) and the ensuing agency costs for equity versus debt.

The result is also consistent with Oranefo and Egbunike (2022) who observed a negative effect of short-term debt to equity on Tobin's Q. The effect of long-term debt to equity and total debt to assets was positive and significant. Hajisaaid (2020) who found that there is a significantly positive relationship between short-term debt and profitability 0.878. A significantly positive association is between long-term debt and profitability 0.638. Hasan; et al (2020) who noted that there is significant relationship on debt financing towards firm profitability. Edore and Ujuju (2020) who found that long term debt

has a significant positive effect on the value of the companies' performance. Medium term debt and short term debts have significant positive influence on value of the companies and were statistically significant.

Onyema (2021) who found that debt financing is statistically significant in determining profitability of manufacturing firms in the quoted firms in Nigeria. The result differs from: Ariyo-Edu (2023) who concluded that debt and profitability are negatively correlated. Atieno (2023) who found that long-term debt financing has a negative and statistically significant effect on the profitability of commercial airlines in Kenya. Amankwah; et al (2021) who found that debt-financed through both short and long term have a detrimental impact on SMEs' financial performance.

Total Equity and Organizational Value

The findings from the Regression Model also reveal that the regression coefficient of Total Equity (TEQ) is positive at 0.074695 while the p-value is 0.0273 ($0.0273 < 0.05$). Based on these findings, the study opines that Total Equity positively and significantly affects Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This result differs from the granger causality test, because the LEQ does not granger cause PFY. The result, however, consistent with The Trade-Off Theory developed by Myers in 1977. The theory states that every company has an optimal capital structure that may be determined by balancing the benefits and drawbacks of equity. The theory argued that a company can ascertain its optimal financial configuration by balancing the benefits of debt (like tax advantages) against the drawbacks of excessive debt (like financial distress) and the ensuing agency costs for equity versus debt. The result is also in agreement with Horsefall (2021) who found that a significant relationship between equity financing and variables of profitability (ROA, ROCE and GPM). Yu and Kim (2023) who observed that a positive correlation between profitability and debt-to-equity ratio for Korean firms.

5. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

The summary of the findings hereunder, were based on the results of the test of the three null hypotheses formulated for the study, the findings from the test and the discussions.

- i. Short Term Debts positively and significantly affects Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. {STD Coefficient is 0.137544, while the p-value is 0.0003 ($0.0003 < 0.05$)}.
- ii. Long Term Debts positively, but insignificantly affects Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. {LTD Coefficient is 0.018702, while the p-value is 0.5479 ($0.5479 > 0.05$)}.
- iii. Total Equity positively and significantly affects Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. {TEQ Coefficient is 0.074695, while the p-value is 0.0273 ($0.0273 < 0.05$)}.

Conclusion

The study evaluated the effect of capital structure on organizational value of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study period was from 2013-2023. The study targeted a total population of twenty-one

(21) consumer goods firms listed on Nigeria Exchange group during the periods. The data collected from the annual audited financial statements of the firms were analyzed using various inferential statistical tools, which include, Descriptive Statistics, Unit Root test, Pairwise Granger Causality test and Panel Least Square Regression Model. Based on the test of the three null hypotheses, the study concludes that, Short Term Debts and Total Equity positively and significantly affect Profit for the Year of consumer goods firms in Nigeria while Long Term Debt positively, but insignificantly affect Profit for the Year of the firms during the period.

Recommendations

The study proposed the following recommendations for the firm managers of the consumer goods firms operating in Nigeria. The recommendations are based on the findings of the study and discussions:

- i. The firm managers of consumer goods firms in Nigeria should use short term debts, such as overdraft, short term loans and trade credit to finance the working capital of their firms. This will ensure that short term business obligations, such as staff salaries, fuel and diesel expense, stationary, car running expenses and so on are settled promptly to sustain business operations.
- ii. The firm managers should also use long term debt to finance their firms' long term investment. This will increase return on investment and organizational value. Examples of long-term debt that can be used to finance long term investment are, credit facilities from bank, debenture stock and loan stocks. However, debt financing should be limited to optimal capital structure to avoid bankruptcy risk.
- iii. The firm managers should also use equity financing when necessary to fund some of its business operations. Thus, the capital structure of the firms should be a combination of debt and equity funding. The advantage of using equity financing is that it does not involve bankruptcy risk.

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